

Puértolas-Pascual, E., Serrano-Martínez, A., Pérez-Pueyo, M., Bádenas, B., & Canudo, J. I. (2022). New data on the neuroanatomy of basal eusuchian crocodylomorphs (Allodaposuchidae) from the Upper Cretaceous of Spain.

The Pyrenees (northeast of Spain) has provided a rich and diverse collection of fossil remains of vertebrates from the Upper Cretaceous, among which the Crocodylomorpha stand out. This record includes remains of the last representatives of the crocodiles of the family Allodaposuchidae, to which the species from the Aragonese record *Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum* and *Agaresuchus subjuniperus* belong. This clade is related to extant crocodiles and disappeared at the same time as non-avian dinosaurs during the Cretaceous-Paleogene (K/Pg) extinction event. In this context, the holotype skull of *Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum* was subjected to a microtomography scanner at the CENIEH facilities to obtain the three-dimensional reconstruction of its internal cranial cavities, including the brain, nerves, blood vessels, paratympnic sinus system and paranasal sinuses. These cavities were compared with those of other crocodylomorphs and it was observed that the endocranial anatomy is consistent with its phylogenetic position within Allodaposuchidae and showing morphologies and neurosensory and cognitive capacities similar to those present in other allodaposuchids. Their inferred sensory capabilities, such as a keen sense of smell and relatively good vision, are within the range observed in most eusuchians and Crocodylia, suggesting that the sensory and cognitive abilities observed in late Mesozoic crocodiles were already similar. to those observed in modern crocodiles.

Figure. Photographs of the holotype skull of *Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum* MPZ 2011/184 and three-dimensional reconstruction of the skull (with transparency) and cranial cavities.

